

p53-Mediated Cancer Resistance in Elephants and Bats: A Comparative Review

Abstract

Cancer has a high mortality rate among humans, however, despite having many more cells than humans, some large and long-lived animals rarely get cancer. This phenomenon here, is known as Peto's paradox, which questions the traditional comprehension of cancer risk in humans. This review explores natural cancer resistance methods seen in elephants and bats and sheds lights on how these biological ways may influence new approaches for human cancer research. Multiple copies of the tumor suppressor gene TP53 has been found in elephants. These along with enhanced apoptosis pathways allow efficient destruction of damaged cells. Similarly, bats, which are long-lived animals with high metabolic activity, show unique DNA repairing process, immunity and oxidative stress tolerance. Altogether, these are thought to contribute to cancer resistance in bats. This review compares these different evolutionary strategies, revealing the key aspect in human cancer biology of p53 involvement in the preservation of genomic stability and the control of cell fate. Even though these mechanisms cannot be directly applied to humans, they offer effective conceptual frameworks to come up with future cancer treatment. The ultimate goal of this review is to provide fundamental ideas in cancer biology and comparative oncology to students and explain how evolutionary biology may be used to guide current cancer studies.

Keywords

Peto's paradox; p53 tumor suppressor; comparative oncology; cancer resistance; elephants; bats; apoptosis; evolutionary cancer biology

Introduction

Cancer remains one of the major health problems even in 21st century, globally imposing high burden on individuals and health care settings. According to World Health Organization (WHO) and its cancer agency, International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), in 2022 alone, approximately 20 million new cancer cases and 9.7 million deaths caused by cancer were reported worldwide. An estimation has been made that, one in five persons will develop cancer during their lifetime and among them one in nine male and one in twelve females will die from the disease. This global cancer burden is variable, as access to diagnosis, treatment and palliative care varies depending on finance of each country. For instance, disproportionately high mortality rate is

observed in low- and middle-income countries (World Health Organization [WHO], 2024). Traditionally, cancer risk has been thought to increase proportionately with how large and long-lived an organism is. However, this expectation is contradicted by findings in nature, a phenomenon called Peto's paradox. Elephants show an amazing example of natural cancer resistance because of the multiple p53 gene copies that they have. Cancer causes 1 in 20 deaths in elephants despite their enormous body size and long lifespan (Gunn, 2023). Similarly, bats have emerged as another striking example of cancer resistance as they show a very low cancer incidence due to enhanced p53 activity while being able to live for several decades (Orr, 2025). Both elephant and bat model challenge the traditional cancer biology and give valuable insights on new cancer defense strategies. This review examines natural cancer resistance mechanism present in some animals like elephants and bats, particularly focusing on the tumor suppressor protein p53 and discusses how these strategies may influence future approaches to human cancer prevention and treatment.

Fundamental concepts of Human Cancer Biology

Cancer is a disease where uncontrolled cell division occurs due to genetic alterations in human cells. Normally, to maintain homeostasis, cell growth and division is strictly regulated and damaged or old cells undergo apoptosis (programmed cell death). When this regulatory system is disrupted by DNA mutations, cells get a chance to proliferate uncontrollably and survive beyond their lifespan and thus cancer arises. These cells further form tumor which can either be benign or malignant. Malignant tumors spread to distant organs by invading surrounding tissues, a process called metastasis. At the molecular level, mutations of some key genes, including proto-oncogenes, tumor suppressor genes and DNA repair genes cause cancer development. Some hallmark features that the cancer cells acquire due to these mutations are: proliferative signaling, resistance to cell death, evasion of immune defense and the ability to induce blood vessel formation (National Cancer Institute, 2025). Tumor suppressor genes refer to some kind of protective genes, which regulate normal cell growth and division. They mainly prevent cells from dividing uncontrollably when DNA damage or cellular stress prevails. TP53, which codes for the p53 protein, is one of the most important tumor suppressor genes in humans as this gene is frequently altered in human cancers (Zhao et al., 2025 & Bartolomei et al., 2025). As of its central role, restoring and increasing

p53 activity has become a major focus in modern cancer research and emerging treatment strategies.

Mechanism of p53 as a Master Regulator of Cell Fate

The tumor suppressor protein p53 is often called the “guardian of the genome” because of its vital role in maintaining genomic stability. At the molecular level, p53 primarily works as a transcription factor which binds to p53 response elements (specific DNA sequences) in the promoters of target genes and perform transcriptional activation or repression. It determines cell fate by regulating the expression of various genes that control cell cycle, repair damaged DNA and eliminate cells with irreversible genetic damage through apoptosis, necrosis and autophagy based on different cellular stresses such as DNA damage, oncogene activation, hypoxia and oxidative stress. Apart from these transcription dependent mechanisms, p53 can also work via protein-protein interactions which is transcription-independent and enables rapid cellular responses to severe damage. Factor like the type and intensity of stress, p53 post-translational modifications, its intracellular localization and cellular context can affect the ultimate outcome of p53 activation. An important function of p53 in tumor suppression is the regulation of multiple forms of cell death which is showed in **Figure 1**. If the stress is moderate, primarily, p53 activates pro-survival responses like cell cycle arrest and autophagy allowing cellular recovery. Under severe or irreparable damage, p53 changes signaling to pro-death pathways to ensure elimination of potentially cancerous cells (Romanova et al., 2026).

Figure 1. *p53-dependent lethal and non-lethal cell death pathways*

Note. From Romanova et al. (2026), *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 27(2), Article 769, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms27020769> (CC BY 4.0).

The most studied p53-mediated cell death pathway in cancer biology is apoptosis which is promoted by p53 via both intrinsic (mitochondrial) and extrinsic (death receptor-mediated) mechanisms. This highly regulated system removes damaged cells with minimal inflammatory consequences. Nonetheless, a phenomenon called anastasis (apoptosis is reversed) may occur in late stages, which adds to therapy resistance. Additionally, p53 regulates necrotic pathways including necroptosis, pyroptosis and ferroptosis. In contrast to apoptosis, such types of cell death tend to cause inflammation and the activation of the immune system. The p53 is involved in regulating membrane permeabilization signaling molecules in necroptosis. It controls transcription of pore-forming proteins and inflammatory caspases in pyroptosis. During ferroptosis, p53 enhances iron-regulated lipid peroxidation through the modulation of cell redox homeostasis and the inhibition of antioxidant mechanisms. This pathway is potentially a good target of therapy because cancer cells resistant to apoptosis are particularly susceptible to ferroptosis. Moreover, p53 has a multifaceted, situation-specific role in autophagy. The nuclear p53 tends to induce the process of autophagy in response to stress through the activation of the energy-sensing and lysosomal pathway and inhibits autophagy during normal conditions, which is done through cytoplasmic p53. Despite the fact that autophagy assists cells to survive, excess or unseemly autophagy may result into the death of cells (Romanova et al., 2026). The dual nature of the autophagy process is highlighted by the fact that in developed cancers, this mechanism may suppress the role of p53 and help tumours to survive.

Figure 2. p53-mediated cellular stress responses and cell fate determination.

Note. From Moulder et al. (2018), *Cancers*, 10(6), 189. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers10060189>

When tumor suppressor genes no longer work, cells lose their natural protection. For TP53, failure mainly occur through missense mutations in the DNA-binding domain, which prevent p53 from binding to its target genes. As a result, mutant p53 loses its tumor-suppressive ability. It also may gain new oncogenic functionality that promote tumor growth, angiogenesis, inflammation and immune evasion within the tumor microenvironment. Furthermore, altered expression of various p53 isoforms can break normal p53 signaling, which allow cancer progression even when the TP53 gene itself is not mutated. An estimation of 50% of all human cancers occur due to mutations that directly inactivate p53, while many other cancers prevail because of the disruption of p53 pathway indirectly by overexpressing its inhibitors such as MDM2 or MDM4 (Bartolomei et al., 2025). MDM2 is an E3 ubiquitin ligase which aims p53 for degradation and nuclear export, illustrated in **Figure 3**. This results in unchecked proliferation and tumor progression (Romanova et al., 2026).

Figure 3. *MDM2–p53 interaction and its role in tumor suppression and cancer progression.*

Note. From Romanova et al. (2026), *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 27(2), Article 769, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms27020769> (CC BY 4.0).

Notably, p53 is a comprehensive regulator which coordinates signaling interaction between apoptosis, necrosis and autophagy. The preference of one pathway over the other is determined by shared signaling elements and metabolic states. Knowledge of these mechanisms is critical in

formulating therapy to reactivate p53 and induce death in cancer cells with minimal adverse effects.

Clinical Relevance of p53

This part demonstrates that p53 modifications are not only hypothetical molecular processes but also directly correlated with the level of aggressiveness of the tumor. Cervical cancer is a bright example of how the downregulation of p53 leads to acceleration of diseases and the worse outcomes of treatment.

Persistent infection with high-risk human papillomavirus (HPV), type 16 and 18 in particular is the primary cause of p53 inactivation in cervical cancer. The viral oncoprotein, E6 enables degradation of p53 by the ubiquitin via the E6-associated protein (E6AP), resulting in reduction of p53 transcriptional activity and suppression of its tumor-protective properties. The E7 oncoprotein also affects the regulation of cell-cycle, supporting uncontrolled cell growth. The decrease in p53 levels prevents apoptosis and cell-cycle arrest caused by DNA-damage and thus permits genetically unstable cells to survive and escape additional oncogenic changes. As a result, cervical cancer cells escape programmed cell death, obtain growth advantage and cause tumor progression and invasion (Wardana et al., 2025).

Low p53 expression is associated with enhanced tumor budding of cervical cancer. Single tumor cells or small groups of up to five cells that detach themselves at the invasive end of the main tumor mass are known as tumor budding. Statistical analysis indicated a strong negative relationship between p53 level and tumor-budding grade ($p = 0.018$; $r = -0.333$) indicating that the lower the p53 the more aggressive the tumor is. Low p53 and high-grade budding cervical tumors are more aggressive in nature as they portray signs of invasion and metastasis. These observations indicate that p53 loss phases are involved in budding based on epithelial mesenchymal transition (EMT), and that low p53 together with high budding can be used as clinically predictive variables (Wardana et al., 2025).

Peto's Paradox

Elephants are great mammals that are made of the same elements as that of humans- cells- but in significantly huge numbers. A single African elephant holds approximately the same number of cells like 100 adult human beings. Since cancer begins when the DNA mutations become

numerous, classical theory predicts that the potential of cancer is far greater in species like elephants due to their increased number of cells and long-life span. However, elephants are very unlikely to get cancer, a phenomenon referred to as Peto's paradox. Elephants maintain low cancer rates since they have been evolved with the effective tumor-suppressive systems. The most interesting one is the fact that the number of additional copies of the TP53 gene, which allows the damaged cells to repair themselves or to self-destruct before turning into malignant cells (Gunn, 2023). The paradox of cancer by Peto shows that nature already found the answer to the big animal cancer problem. The investigation of such evolutionary adaptations covers a gap between human cancer biology and animal models and provides new concepts on cancer prevention and treatment.

Figure 4. Illustration of Peto's paradox showing that cancer risk does not increase with body mass and lifespan across species, despite theoretical expectations.

Note. From Tollis et al. (2017), *Peto's paradox*, Arizona State University, via EurekaAlert!.

Cancer Resistance Mechanisms in Elephants

Elephants are remarkably resistant to cancer despite having a large body size and a high cell count due to their improved tumor suppressor mechanisms based on the p53. Unlike humans, who have a single copy of the TP53 gene, elephants have approximately 20 copies, many of which are TP53 retrogenes, giving them a higher gene dosage and a higher level of genomic surveillance. It ensures that their cells can recognize DNA damage more easily and that malignant cells have a lower chance of evading control. Moreover, instead of attempting to repair their DNA they follow 'shoot

first' approach leading to an increased rate of apoptosis ensuring that damaged cells get destroyed quickly. Elephant cells are more susceptible to DNA damage and are likely to face apoptosis about twice as human which limits the survival and proliferation of potential cancer cells. A number of TP53 retrogenes in elephants encode truncated p53-like proteins which also have apoptotic value and may induce cell death via mitochondria. An additional tumor suppressor pathway further enhances the increased rate of apoptosis which is enabled by the leukemia inhibitory factor (LIF) gene, particularly the refunctionalized LIF6 “zombie gene”. Upon activated by p53 in response to DNA damage, it can cause mitochondrial apoptosis via Bak/Bax-mediated membrane permeabilization which is shown in **Figure 5**. This enables a redundant fail-safe mechanism for damaged cell elimination (Reyes Castro et al., 2023; Gunn, 2023). The combination of having multiple copies of TP53, increased rates of apoptosis and activation of LIF equips elephants with a multi-faceted system to combat cancer.

Figure 5. *LIF6-induced apoptosis through a Bak/Bax-mediated mitochondrial pathway.*

Note. Reproduced from Reyes Castro et al. (2023), *Journal of Student Research*, 12(4), Article 5377. Adapted from Vazquez et al. (2018). <https://doi.org/10.47611/jsrhs.v12i4.5377>

Cancer Resistance Mechanisms in Bats

Bats are highly metabolic and unusually long-lived despite their small size, which would increase their vulnerability to cancer. However, that is not the case in reality due to their unique and highly efficient cancer-resistance mechanisms, providing an alternative evolutionary tumor suppression

pattern to the large mammals such as the elephant. Molecular evidence to these resistance mechanisms has been obtained using comparative genomic and cellular studies demonstrating that, long-lived bat species have an elevated basal p53 transcriptional activity, an augmented p53-mediated apoptosis in response to genotoxic stress, regulatory modulation system carried by factors like MDM2 and WRAP53 and a persistent telomerase activity (illustrated in **Figure 6.**) in the somatic tissues. These eliminate potentially cancerous cells without excessive cell loss. It is important to note that active sequences of telomerase have been demonstrated by experimental telomerase repeat amplification assays in bat somatic cells and tissues, which allow the long-term proliferation of cells and tissues without the oncogenic effects that are seen in small-body mammals. Moreover, the bats have strong immune surveillance, reduced chronic inflammation and effective anti-tumor immune responses, which means that they can effectively clear up the damaged or abnormal cells (Orr, 2025; Athar et al., 2025). These mechanisms are organized and interconnected, which makes bats resistant to cancer and a good source of information on the prevention of human cancer and age-related treatment in the future.

Figure 6. Bat cells and tissues possess telomerase activity. *Reproduced from Athar et al. (2025), Nature Communications, 16(1), Article 4125, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-59403-z>. © 2025 Athar et al., distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.*

Comparative Analysis of Cancer Resistance Between Humans, Elephants and Bats

A relative analysis of the human species, the elephants and the bats shows the differences in evolutionary strategies that may lead to the successful elimination of cancer even when the body mass, lifespan and metabolism of the species differ significantly. The cancer predisposition is quite high in humans and this has been attributed to dependence on a unit copy of TP53 gene and moderate apoptotic reactions, which are easily damaged due to the occurrence of mutations or the inhibitory effect of regulatory factors. Despite the human inherent capacity to repair DNA and immune surveillance activities, those systems tend to be ineffective in opposing accumulated genetic damage in the course of time especially when the p53 signaling is impaired.

In contrast, elephants possess the extreme mode of tumor suppression due to their genetic redundancy and hypersensitivity to DNA damage. The existence of around 20 copies of TP53 substantially increases genomic care and encourages hasty apoptosis as opposed to healing and thus eradicates the potentially cancerous cells prior to an increase in clonal development. Despite of this huge cell count and long-life expectancy, cancer risks are minimized with this "shoot first" strategy. Moreover, other supporting pathways like LIF6 also mediate mitochondrial apoptosis to add on to this well-organized defense system.

An alternative approach is observed in Bats which is fundamentally different and equally effective. Instead of duplication of genes, bats depend on a high degree of regulation of p53 activity, efficient processes of repairing the DNA, a high level of immune surveillance and controlled inflammation. Their capacity to stay alive and remain able to maintain telomerase activity in their somatic tissues without inducing oncogenesis coupled with a balanced apoptotic response enables them to maintain tissues throughout their lives and avoid malignant transformation. The elimination strategy of the bats is different as compared to that of the elephants; contrary to the aggressive elimination strategy, the bats keep the tissue intact but maintain cancer resistance, which is an adaptation to high metabolic stress during flight.

From this comparative analysis, it can be concluded that cancer resistance is not achieved via one universal mechanism rather through the optimization of various tumor suppressor pathways in particular species.

Implications for Future Cancer Therapies

The research on cancer-resistant organisms including elephants and bats is a good source of conceptualizations that can be applied to enhance human cancer treatment, especially one involving tumor suppression and not tumor destruction. Although humans cannot directly embrace these evolutionary adaptations, the concept of how nature has optimized p53 signaling, apoptosis, immune regulation and genomic stability can be used to guide novel treatment approaches that enhance already existing treatments. Notably, the approaches are meant to be considered as biologically informative models and not direct templates that should be used in the clinic.

Enhancing p53 Activity

Since p53 is central in tumor suppressions in the human, elephant and bat species, p53 restoration or promotion is one of the most promising therapeutic approaches to cancer. Stabilization of p53, or restoration of p53 transcriptional activity and/or manipulation of downstream signaling pathways might re-establish p53 functionalities in cancer cells in human cancers and potentially allow the cancer cells to regulate their own cell cycle and enhance the destruction of genetically unstable cells. Also, it has been noted that p53 exist in different isoforms which implies that specific isoforms can be selectively modulated to provide fine control over p53 responses, with tumor suppression and minimum harm to normal tissues. Bats sustain high basal p53 level but do not cause excessive apoptosis, which can be taken as an insight that balance is more important than maximality in therapy.

Imitating the Redundancy of Elephants

Elephants show that genetic redundancy may deliver extraordinary cancer protection by decreasing the dependence on one pathway of tumor suppressor. As it is neither possible nor safe to introduce several copies of TP53 in humans, the general principle of functional redundancy gives a valuable therapeutic inspiration. The defect of one of the pathways can be compensated by the activation of numerous and parallel tumor suppressive pathways that include apoptosis, responding to DNA damage and mitochondrial cell death. Inspired from the multi-layered defense system of the elephant, the combined therapy involving multiple regulatory networks can potentially be more effective than single-agent therapy. Instead of replicating genes, human cancer therapy can endeavor to restore redundancy on the pathway and signaling scale.

Immunomodulatory and Anti-inflammatory Treatments

Bats offer an interesting example of tumor immunomodulation. They can effectively eliminate damaged or abnormal cells without stimulating tumor supportive inflammatory conditions due to their capacity to have a robust immune surveillance and to suppress chronic inflammation. The balance relates especially to human cancer because chronic inflammation is a well-known cause of tumor formation and development. Bat biology can aid therapeutic interventions to gain an improved understanding of immune mediated tumor recognition at minimal tissue inflammatory damage. These ideas are in agreement with cancer immunotherapy these days and the idea is that immune modulation and not immune overstimulation is the key to long-term cancer control.

Notably, these therapeutic implications are inspirational but not transferable. The evolutionary changes in elephants and bats occurred over millions of years under the constraints of each species and such processes should be translated into human medicine with a lot of care towards safety, feasibility and biological background.

Limitations and Future Directions

Although much has been learned by studying the cancer resistant species, a number of limitations need to be put into consideration when applying the findings to the biology of human cancer. Human beings are not elephants or bats and the evolutionary changes under which these animals safeguard themselves against cancer evolved within the physiological, ecological and genetic constraints of species. Direct copying of these mechanisms in humans (especially genetic manipulation) has serious biological hazards, such as unintended effects on development, tissue homeostasis and aging.

A big weakness is that the p53 signaling in human beings is intricate. Although the improved p53 activity is protective in elephants and highly regulated in bats, in humans, excess or unregulated p53 activity can result in counterproductive effects of tissue degeneration, inhibition of regeneration or aging. In the same manner, the preservation of the telomerase in somatic cells as it is found in bats is oncogenic in humans because of the variation in control.

The other issue is the partial knowledge in interspecies variations in immune control, metabolism and lifespan. The existing experimental models might not be able to capture these long-time evolutionary adaptations which are very complex. Also, there are moral restrictions on how far genetic or systemic alterations can be experimented on humans inspired from animal models.

Thus, future research must aim at doing comparative oncology studies in more species to outline the conserved principles of tumor-suppression rather than species-specific characteristics. Combining genomics, transcriptomics, immunology and systems biology in an integrative way may assist in discovering regulatory patterns, which are flexible to human biology. Notably, safe, reversible and accurate regulation of therapeutic development should be emphasized in the future as opposed to irreversible genetic modifications.

Conclusion

Cancer resistance is not restricted to humans nor does cancer occur only due to large body size or long lifespan. The presence of extremely cancer-resistant species like elephants and bats proves that evolution has already acquired effective mechanisms of inhibiting tumor formation at the expense of various biological solutions. The key to such mechanisms is the tumor suppressor protein p53, which plays the role of a global controller of immune interaction, genomic stability and cell fate across the species.

The elephants have to depend on genetic redundancy and increased apoptotic sensitivity, whereas, bats have to fine-tune DNA repair, immune surveillance and inflammation control. Through these divergent but successful adaptations, it is notable that cancer suppression may be attained by taking various evolutionary paths. The analysis of such natural models enhances the knowledge of the human tumor biology and disproves the conventional beliefs in the study of human cancer.

Even though the mechanisms are not directly applicable to humans, they offer strong conceptual models to the generation of future cancer therapies. Through the study of these natural solutions, human medicine will be able to proceed towards more effective, balanced and evolution-informed approaches to cancer prevention and treatment. After all, comparative oncology can do more than just broaden the scientific knowledge of people, it can also support the notion that the study of life through the lens of different species can enhance the health of people.

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